

Targeted Metabolomics Sample Preparation

ID: SP000A-X

Authors	¹ Tabea Wiedmer, ¹ Abigail Jarret, ¹ Sabrina Lindinger
Affiliations	¹ CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine. Vienna, AT.

Protocol description

Protocol for intracellular metabolite extraction from different cell lines for targeted metabolomics measurement using a 6-well or 24-well plate format.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 1321N1 human brain (astrocytoma) Origin: ECACC through SIGMA Order No.: 86030402-1VL▪ HCT 116 Colo-Rectal Carcinoma Origin: ATCC Order No.: CCL-247▪ JumpIN T-Rex HEK293 Origin: Life Technologies through Fisher Scientific Austria Order No.: K1889 (part of Kit Nr A15008)▪ HuH-7 hepatocarcinoma Origin: JCRB Order No.: JCRB0403▪ LS180 colon adenocarcinoma Origin: ECACC through SIGMA Order No.: 87021202-1VL▪ SK-MEL-28 malignant melanoma Origin: ATCC/LGCgenomics through ATCC Order No.: HTB-72 <p>The parental cell lines were genetically modified by either knocking out individual SLC genes or overexpressing individual SLC genes under a doxycycline inducible promoter. The appropriate cell line model for each SLC was chosen based on its expression across the panel of cell lines described above and the feasibility to generate knockout cell lines.</p> <p>https://re-solute.eu/resources/reagents</p>
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium - high glucose (DMEM) Product: D5796-500mL Manufacturer: SIGMA▪ RPMI- 1640 Medium With L-glutamine and sodium bicarbonate, liquid, sterile-filtered, suitable for cell culture Product: R8758-500ML

	<p>Manufacturer: SIGMA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Fetal Bovine Serum Product: 10270-106 LOT: 42F8381K <p>Manufacturer: GIBCO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Penicillin-Streptomycin (10,000 U/mL) Product: 15140-122 Manufacturer: Gibco▪ Doxycycline hyclate Product: D9891-1G Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich▪ 1X Dulbeccos PBS without Ca & Mg 1x500mls (Sigma) Product: D8537-500ML Manufacturer: Sigma▪ Poly-L-Lysine Product: P6282-5MG Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich▪ Ammonium Carbonate Product: 207861-500G Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich▪ Molecular Biology Grade Water Product: 46-000-CV Manufacturer: Corning▪ Formic Acid 98-100% Product: 1.00264.0100 Manufacturer: Merck▪ Water, for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83645.320 Manufacturer: VWR▪ Methanol for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83638.32 Manufacturer: VWR <p>Internal Standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ LABELED CARNITINE STANDARDS SET B in 10 vials Product: NSK-B Manufacturer: Cambridge Isotope Laboratories through Euriso- top GMBH
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Folic acid-(glutamic acid-13C5,15N) Product: 803162-1MG Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ METABOLOMICS AMINO ACID MIX STANDARD Product: MSK A2-1.2 Manufacturer: Cambridge Isotope Laboratories through Euriso- top GMBH ▪ TAURINE (1,2-13C2, 98%) Product: CLM-6622-0.25 Manufacturer: Cambridge Isotope Laboratories through Euriso- top GMBH ▪ Adenosine-13C10,15N5 5'-monophosphate disodium salt solution Product: 650676-1MG Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ Uridine-13C9,15N2 5'-monophosphate disodium salt solution Product: 651370-1MG Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ 2'-Deoxyadenosine-13C10,15N5 5'-monophosphate disodium salt solution Product: 900386-1MG Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ Citric acid-1,5-13C2 Product: 488607-100mg Manufacturer: Sigma Aldrich ▪ METABOLITE YEAST EXTRACT (U-13C, 98%) Product: ISO1 Manufacturer: Isotopic solutions E.U.
Equipment:	

Reagents setup

Ammonium Carbonate Buffer

Ammonium Carbonate: 96,09g/mol

- 3,6g Ammonium Carbonate per 500ml H₂O
- Adjust the pH with formic acid to pH 7.4
- sterile filter the buffer

Procedure

Sample preparation from 6-well plate for targeted metabolomics

1. Prepare quadruplicate wells in 6 well plate.
2. Coat the plates with Poly-L-Lysine (only for HEK293 cells): add 1ml Poly-L-Lysine into each well

Incubate 5min
Put the Poly-L-Lysine back to the Falcon
Wash with at least 5ml H₂O each well (5ml water can be reused for about 3 wells)
Remove the H₂O and let the plate dry (need to be completely dry!!)
3. Count cells and seed 750 000/well HEK cells in 2 ml complete medium; to be 70-80% confluent the next day.
For each cell line, plate 4 replicates without Doxycycline and 4 replicates with Doxycycline (1µg/mL Doxycycline added to complete medium while seeding cells).
4. Incubate 24h at 37°C in complete medium (10% FBS + 1% P/S).
5. Check and adjust the pH of the Ammonium Carbonate Buffer every time before using it. Adjust with formic acid.
6. Take the plate to the lab and wash gently with 1000µl 75mM Ammonium carbonate Buffer pH 7.4 at room temperature.
7. Transfer the plate to ice and add 1500 µl/well of 80:20 ice-cold MeOH:H₂O solution (pre-cooled at -80°C and on dry ice).
8. Scrape cells and transfer everything to Eppendorf tube (pre-cooled on dry ice). Use the same cell scraper for the 4 replicates.
9. Snap freeze tubes in liquid nitrogen immediately.
10. Thaw samples on ice.
11. Centrifuge at max. speed at 4°C for 10 min.
12. Transfer supernatant into an HPLC vial (pre-cooled in metal rack on ice).

13. Evaporate samples or store at -80°C.
14. Reconstitute samples in water and add internal standard mixture to each.
15. Proceed with LC-MS analysis.

Sample preparation from 24-well plate for targeted metabolomics

1. Prepare quadruplicate wells in 24 well plate.
2. Coat the plates with Poly-L-Lysine (only for HEK293 cells): add 500µl Poly-L-Lysine into each well

Incubate 5min

Wash with at least 1ml H₂O each well (water can be reused for about 3 wells)

Remove the H₂O and let the plate dry (need to be completely dry!!)

1. Count cells and seed the previously tested number of cells in 1 ml complete medium; to be 70-80% confluent the next day).

plate 150 000 cells per well for the
HCT116 and LS180

plate 100 000 cells per well for 1321N1

plate 50 000 cells per well for HuH7

plate 70 000 cells per well for SKMEL

For each cell line, plate 4 replicates without Doxycycline and 4 replicates with Doxycycline (1µg/mL Doxycycline added to complete medium while seeding cells).

2. Incubate 24h at 37°C in complete medium (10% FBS + 1% P/S).
3. Check and adjust the pH of the Ammonium Carbonate Buffer every time before using it. Adjust with formic acid to pH 7.4.
4. Take the plate to the main lab and wash gently with 500µl 75mM Ammonium carbonate Buffer pH 7.4 at room temperature.
5. Transfer the plate to ice and add 300 µl/well of 80:20 ice-cold MeOH:H₂O solution including the internal standards already (pre-cooled at -80°C and on dry ice).
6. Scrape cells and transfer everything to an Eppendorf tube (pre-cooled on dry ice). Use the same cell scraper for the 4 replicates.
7. Snap freeze tubes in liquid nitrogen immediately.
8. Thaw samples on ice.
9. Centrifuge at max. speed at 4°C for 10 min.
10. Transfer supernatant into an HPLC vial (pre-cooled in metal rack on ice).
11. Evaporate samples or store at -80°C.

<http://re-solute.eu>
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12. Proceed with LC-MS analysis.

Additional notes

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/metabolomics>

References

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/reagents>

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.